

Impact of Social Media Advertising on Purchase Intention: Mediation of Advertising Literacy, Influencer Review, E-Lifestyle and Brand Awareness

Fizza Tahir¹, Asma Nisar², Maryam Rehmat³

Abstract

The research project under consideration examines how social media advertising and purchase intention is related, with advertising literacy, influencer review, brand awareness and e-lifestyle serving as a strong link and developing a mediation between the social media advertising and purchase intention. The study focused on the field of social media advertising. Institutions and working places in Lahore were picked who had purchase any product online through social sites. The purposive sampling technique was used to obtain information from a sample of 235 consumers. The time horizon was one shot cross sectional survey. Following data collection, analysis was carried out by using Process Macro Hayes mediation model 4 in SPSS, two statistical programs utilized for the evaluation and testing of the responses gathered. The data were subjected to reliability, correlation, and regression analysis. In addition, the data were run through a double mediation model (Model 4) to test the hypotheses. The findings showed that the hypotheses were positively significant and confirmed by the data. The latest study is a contribution to the literature in general and broadens the range of variables that may influence social media advertisement. It improves knowledge and comprehension of the variables and their relationships, which can aid in developing effective and efficient tactics that brands can employ to inspire their customers to build a solid platform of brand awareness.

Keywords: Social media advertising, purchase intention, advertising literacy, influencer review, e-lifestyle, brand awareness

1. Introduction

Social media is progressively uncovering a spot for itself in every facet of human lives (Yasir et al., 2021). Consumers nowadays are connected with social media platforms such as YouTube, Snapchat, Instagram, Facebook. Social media has expanded rapidly and has hooked vast number of audiences in the last few years (Atiq et al., 2022; Dao et al., 2014). According to the research, organizations globally have started explaining about how using these platforms might help in attaining consumers and constructing a strong profitable marketing relationship with consumers. Influencer marketing, celebrity endorsements has become marketing device as it proposes commitments with vast numbers of consumers at lower cost in little time than usual advertising (Evans et al., 2017). The increase in influencer marketing on social sites has improved the duty of brands to properly advertise in a clear and prominent meaning (Nil & Alberts, 2014). The current study of social media advertising with respect to different mediating variables leading to purchase intention is less frequently explored. Influencer review, E-lifestyle, Brand awareness and advertising literacy are some dynamics that can be lead to purchase intention by the help of social media advertisements. Social media marketing theory of David Chaffey has been applied to link in developing a relation between social media elements and awareness contributing to purchase intention. It is difficult to stand out from the competition on social media platforms in every business sector and gain the whole attention of consumers and look into their liking and disliking. Social media advertisement is critical in this competitive environment for brand's existence and consumer preferences. Low level of display advertisement shown with respect to competition may lead to lower level of purchase intention as there's low level of brand trust and awareness. Research shows that there is less work done on social media advertising that connects purchasing behavior of people through influencer reviews and impulse buying (Athar et al., 2021; Mukhtar et al., 2021). The gap identified in this study is that the factors influencing the whole process of buying from social media advertising will be brand awareness, e-lifestyle, advertising literacy and influencer review. It can be argued that these social sites marketing also results in increase of brand awareness and advertising literacy. People can see different types of ads from the same brand and different ads convey different information. When a user is shown multiple ads of the same brand, they tend to learn more about the brand which increases their knowledge, thus aiding advertising literacy. More exposure to the brand also means increased brand awareness and recognition. The research objectives of this study are: First, to identify a significant relationship between social media advertising and purchased intention considering E-lifestyle. Second, to identify the level of brand awareness considering the significant relationship between social media advertising and purchase intention. Third, to identify the relationship between social media advertising and purchase intention considering influencer review. Fourth, to identify a significant relationship between social media advertising and purchased intention considering advertising literacy.

2. Theoretical Framework of the study

2.1. Social media advertising, Advertising Literacy and Purchase Intention

Advertisements displayed on social media platforms to serve social media users are known as social media advertising (Atiq et al., 2022). Social media advertisements are the form of internet advertisements (Alalawan et al., 2017). Advertisements are shown on social sites to reach its target audience and the vast number of social media users helps

¹ Mphil, Department of Business Administration, Kinnaird College for Women, Lahore, Pakistan

² Corresponding Author, Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Kinnaird College for Women, Lahore, Pakistan

³ Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Kinnaird College for Women, Lahore, Pakistan

in completing this task (Muhazim & Abu Bakar, 2015). Advertisements displayed on social media platforms to serve social media users are known as social media advertising (Alalawan et al., 2017). Advertising literacy tells how much knowledge individual have about the advertisement. It is defined as to keep conceptual knowledge of advertising (Rozendaal et al., 2011). Information about the advertising techniques their persuasive aim targets the audience. Advertising is a distinctive practice of communication. Special literacy skills are required to understand and interpret this communication (Nando, 2010). Advertising literacy's immediate affect leads to positive result. Children, adults nowadays keep a considerate knowledge about social media advertisement than traditional media advertising (Ritson & Elliot, 1995). Awareness about brand and knowledge about the advertisement makes the brand achieve its goal to advertise the brand (Dam & Rejimersdal, 2019). Advertisements are the reminders for consumers, to raise awareness, determination to buy and alter submissive purchasers into consumers. At the end of advertisement, then buyer decides whether to purchase the product or not (Talih & Golbasi, 2017). Social media advertisement is valuable they create millions of views, like and followers on social sites. Through this, users got to know about the companies, prices and product range quicker than other customers. This also provides great advantages(Talih & Golbasi, 2017). Purchase intention is the desire of a customer's to buy any service / product looking at their quality (Rukh et al., 2021; Yasir et al., 2021). It is the decision-making process that a customer goes through to buy from specific brand. (Akbariyeh et al., 2015). It is defined as a condition where customer's buys a certain product under certain circumstances. This is actually a dependent variable which depends upon different factors like satisfaction, likings etc.

H1: Social media advertising has a positive relationship with advertising literacy.

H5: Advertising literacy acts as mediator between social media advertising and purchase intention.

H9: Advertising literacy has a positive relationship with purchase intention.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

2.2. Social media advertising, Influencer review and Purchase Intention

Social media platforms are the new place where people, government, organizations can, commercially, educationally, and politically convey to each other and interchange thoughts, services, goods and content (Chen & Zhu, 2015). Influencer review is considered as electronic word of mouth. They assess the service or product and share their experience. Reviews coming from influencers hold immense power (Guruge, 2018). Their feedback influences purchase intention (Nelson et al., 2019). Direct marketing is done between the influencers and brand. This form of advertising is done on social media platforms through stories or post. (Nelson et al., 2019). Influencers are the vanguard of social media trends. They are the trendsetters who generate new content that makes them on top of every social media user (Kadekova & Holeincinova, 2018). Influencers enliven social media through their creativity and spread them on social media so that people can follow them (Duan & Whinston, 2008). They directly communicate with target audience and suggest product and brand recommendation in appropriate way(Gerrath & Usrey, 2020). The influencer reviews are given in exchange for free products, payment or invitations (Ananda & Wandebari, 2016). Their real-life tutorials increase the customer's trustworthiness as they use the product on themselves and then recommend others (Nelson et al., 2019). Influencer reviews are the newest method to the marketing. They do not market as a whole but focuses on those individuals who are in a decision-making process (Tjahjana et al., 2020). However, sometimes this forced review question's the influencer's validity and credibility (Petrescu et al., 2021). If the influencer keeps the brand's review more personal regardless of what the consumers are reviewing that reviews

do not hold any credibility in the society (Mayzlin & PEI, 2022). The intention of any consumer to purchase particular product explains that they will buy in future to satisfy their wants and needs (Naseri et al., 2023). These influencer discuss unspoken messages about the brand and products which receivers perceive as non-advertisements of the brand and trust those communicators more in general (Dwidienawati et al., 2020).

H2: Social media advertising has a positive relationship with influencer review.

H6: Influencer review acts as mediator between social media advertising and purchase intention.

H10: Influencer review has a positive relationship with purchase intention.

2.3. Social media advertising, E-lifestyle and purchase intention

Lifestyle is a set of patterns in which people dedicate their money (Ali, 2022) and time and E- Lifestyle is actually how people devote their time and money to social sites (Ali, 2022). It is also about why people do and what they do. The merging of mobile and internet usage, in all age groups has molded the way people live since last few decades (Ramayah et al., 2015). Lifestyle is normally linked to establish the relation between demographic variables to interactive models for persons, technology-dependent products and services. E-lifestyle has been connected with information technology and communication assisted services and products (Chanaron & Jean, 2013). E-lifestyle can offer marketers with a valuable base for designing services and marketing purposes for consumers. Lately, by equipping the most up-to-date and inclusive summary of lifestyle theory, it was recommended that daily routine, lifestyle is a set of performances originated by motivation (Yu & Chain, 2015). It is grown up by interaction with different conditions like environmental situations and this is formed by perception, choices beliefs and conditions. All the theories including expectancy value theory, human motivation and personal construction theory, all these are created from psychology and sociology. So, from sociological standpoint, lifestyle is driven by external stimuli and from psychology standpoint, lifestyle is introduced by internal belief. These both leads to the use of electronic and digital media. (Rachbini et al., 2018). E-lifestyle is necessary because it opens an international marketplace for business which is restricted by geographical zones (Ramayah et al., 2015; Ali, 2022). So, the present researches adapt that e-lifestyle is based on four interconnected gears; e-opinions, e-interests, e-values, e-activities. E-opinions include politics, economics, education, production etc. E-values contains fulfillment, accomplishment, Hopes, demands etc. E-interests include fashion, media, family, job, home, achievements etc. E-activities comprise of work, social events, hobbies, sports, shopping etc. These measurements examine person's sociological and psychological significance of e-lifestyle. (Hassan et al., 2017). Different constituents such as recommendation from friends, family or online reviews influence a person's e-lifestyle which develops purchase intention (Qin et al., 2021). In addition to this, the easy accessibility and suitability for online shopping by seeing social media advertisements has divert the purchasing intention and behavior of consumers (Wijaya et al., 2020).

H3: Social media advertising has a positive relationship with E-lifestyle.

H7: E-lifestyle acts as mediator between social media advertising and purchase intention.

H11: E-lifestyle has a positive significant relationship with purchase intention.

2.4. Social media advertising, Brand awareness and purchase intention

Brand awareness is how to alert customers about the brand and its product (Chabot & Gustafson, 2007). Brand awareness help the companies to keep their product updated. They get to know whether their product is being liked by customers or not (Rossiter & Sarigollu, 2000). Brand awareness is the brand's identity, it is the complete information a customer needs to buy from that brand. "Brand awareness is the initial step in ride to brand knowledge and brand attitude". Brand awareness is the tool which only can make consumer decide rapidly. Enhancing brand awareness rules on the memory of consumers which leads to purchase of an item (Athar et al., 2021; MacInnis et al., 1999). Brand awareness level must be so high that brand name reminds the need to purchase that particular. In this era, brand awareness is spread widely though social media advertising. If a person is well aware of the brand he would definitely buy the product and if not, the social media advertisements play an important role in spreading the brand name. Customer's purchase decision also depends upon if he has brand awareness (Percy et al., 1992). "Brand awareness" is measured by purchasing from that brand or recalls a brand name when you want that specific product or service (Rahm, 2022). Brand awareness has a vital role in purchase intention because customer's buy those products which they are well aware of. Brand awareness helps a brand to get more customers to their doorstep or landing page (Susilowati et al., 2020). Consumers prefer to buy those brands which are already known in the market. Consumers become loyal to business by their quality, style, easy usage, pricing strategy etc (Afroze et al., 2021). All these objectives attract consumers towards the brand and proper advertisements if done properly leads to purchase of that product (Dennhardt et al., 2013).

H4: Social media advertising has a positive relationship with Brand awareness.

H8: Brand awareness acts as mediator between social media advertising and purchase intention.

H12: Brand awareness has a positive relationship with purchase intention.

3. Research Methodology

The goal of this research is to determine the effect of independent variable (social media advertisement) on dependent variable (purchase intention), as well as the mediating effects of the advertising literacy, influencer review, e-lifestyle, brand awareness on the purchase intention. The research setting is non-contrived. The study contains the individuals,

organizations as the unit of investigation. The study embroils around the students, adults, parents, organizations, and social media users. The data collection period is devoted to as the time frame. The data is composed at a specific point in time from a large number of consumers in a cross-sectional approach. Universities in Lahore were picked from the population by using random selection procedures. Purposive sampling is used. The sample consists of 230 responses because the sample size was calculated using Nunnally's (1978) assumption of ten times the number of items in the questionnaire, i.e. ($23 \times 10 = 230$). For the pilot study, 5 replies will be added. The questionnaire was circulated among the respondents, who are of both genders and all ages, through various social media networks. The target audience are the persons aged between 18 to 45. Google forms were shared on different social sites so that respondents can fill them at their ease. Seven segments completed the questionnaire. Five-point Likert scale was used to measure the variables, where 1 is the minimum desirable response and 5 is the strongest favorable response.

3.1. Measures

Standard measuring scales will be used to measure the study's variables. A five-point Likert scale will be used to evaluate each variable. There is further information in Table 1.

Table 1

Variables	No. of Items	Sample Items	References
Social media advertising	4	Social media advertising is an authentic source of product information and provide relevant information.	(Alalwan, 2018)
Influencer review	4	I often read influencer review to know product impression by others.	(Michelle R. Nelson, 2019)
Advertising literacy	4	Commercials on social sites are there to make you think positively about the advertised product.	(Malmelin, 2010)
E-lifestyle	4	E-lifestyle chosen services/products greatly enhance the convenience of my life.	(Hassan, 2015)
Brand awareness	3	I am always aware of this brand.	(CHABOT, 2007)
Purchase intention	4	I am likely to purchase goods that are encouraged on social media.	(Hamid Akbariyeh, 2015)

4. Results

4.1. Data analysis approach

For data analysis SPSS and PROCESS programme was used based on the previous study (Rana et al., 2021). In direction to regulate the associations between the variables, regression analysis was used. We established the fourth model using the SPSS and PROCESS model templates.

Table 2: Reliability Test

Variables	Items	Alpha
Social media advertising	4	0.700
Influencer review	4	0.731
Advertising literacy	4	0.667
E- Lifestyle	4	0.725
Brand awareness	3	0.620
Purchase intention	4	0.744

4.2. Interpretation

Since the Cronbach's Alpha values for the four variables: Social media advertising, Influencer review, and E-lifestyle, Purchase Intention are all above 0.7, the results are respected as reliable. In addition to this, the values of the mediators Brand awareness and Advertising Literacy are all less than 0.7, which shows that these two variables could create reliable data values for the study.

4.3. Interpretation

The results of the correlation analysis indicates that Social media advertising and Influencer review ($r=0.652$, $p<0.05$) has a strong positive and linear relationship. It indicates that rate of increase in Social media advertising also leads to increase in Influencer review and vice versa. Social media advertising and Advertising literacy ($r=0.615$, $p<0.05$) signals that there is moderate positive relationship. It proposes that social media advertising in business can lead to

advertising literacy. Social media advertising and E-lifestyle ($r=0.520$, $p<0.05$) implies that a moderate positive relationship. It results in that social media advertising leads to maintain an E-lifestyle. ($r=0.579$, $p<0.05$) The value is resulted in a moderate positive relationship between social media advertising and Brand awareness. It explains that social media advertising assists in increasing the brand awareness. The value ($r=0.577$, $p<0.05$) is resulted in a moderate positive relationship between social media advertising and purchase intention. It states that social media advertising helps in purchase intention. The value ($r=0.577$, $p<0.05$) is resulted in a moderate positive relationship between social media advertising and purchase intention. It states that social media advertising helps in purchase intention. The value ($r=0.626$, $p<0.05$) explains that there is a moderate positive relationship between Influencer review and Advertising Literacy. It says that influencer review leads to advertising literacy. The value ($r=0.595$, $p<0.05$) states that there is a moderate positive relationship between Influencer review and E-lifestyle. Influencer review has an impact on E-lifestyle. Influencer review and Brand awareness have a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.563$, $p<0.05$).

Table 3: Correlational Analysis

Correlations						
Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
SMA	1					
IR	.652**	1				
AL	.615**	.626**	1			
EL	.520**	.595**	.652**	1		
BA	.579**	.563**	.658**	.659**	1	
PI	.577**	.614**	.638**	.689**	.702**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results represents that Influencer review effects the Brand awareness for the brand. The value ($r=0.614$, $p<0.05$) shows that there is a moderate positive relationship between Influencer review and Purchase Intention. If an Influencer review of brand is strong it will result in purchase intention with the brand. Advertising Literacy and E-lifestyle has a moderate strong relationship($r=0.652$, $p<0.05$). The results show that constructive spread of advertising literacy increases and E-lifestyle. Advertising literacy and Brand awareness have a moderate strong relationship($r=0.658$, $p<0.05$). This explains that advertising literacy spreads from Brand awareness. The values ($r=0.638$, $p<0.05$) shows that advertising literacy and purchase intention have a moderate positive relationship. It pictures that a brand that generates advertising literacy for their customers results in purchase intention. The value ($r=0.659$, $p<0.05$) resulted in producing a strong positive relationship between E-lifestyle and Brand awareness. Growth in E-lifestyle and Brand awareness. E-lifestyle and Purchase Intention has a moderate positive relationship($r=0.658$, $p<0.05$) that means better the e-lifestyle more the purchase intention of consumers. The value ($r=0.702$, $p<0.05$) shows that there is a strong positive relationship between Brand awareness and Purchase Intention. The increase in brand awareness leads to more purchase for the brand.

4.4. Regression Analysis

Social media advertising – advertising literacy – purchase intention

Model = 4

Y = MPI

X = MSMA

M = MAL

4.5. Analysis Notes

Bootstrap confidence intervals: 1000

Level of confidence : 95.00

4.6. Interpretation: Model 1 Summary

The value of R shows that the relationship is 61.47% between social media advertising and advertising literacy. The value of R square is 37.7%, depicts the amount of modification in advertising literacy, due to social media advertising, is 37.7%. The value of f ($F=141.50$) and $p=0.000$, shows that the model is good suited.

Independent variable

+ve
Mediator

Table 4
Sample size = 235

Outcome: Advertising Literacy						
Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6147	.3778	.2838	141.5012	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	1.3925	.2121	6.5665	.0000	.9747	1.8103
MSMA	.6313	.0531	11.8954	.0000	.5268	.7359
Outcome: Purchase Intention						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6793	.4614	.2424	99.3677	2.0000	232.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.9325	.2134	4.3709	.0000	.5122	1.3529
MAL	.4511	.0605	7.4502	.0000	.3318	.5704
MSMA	.3023	.0622	4.8604	.0000	.1797	.4248
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL						
Outcome: MPI						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5766	.3325	.2991	116.0763	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5607	.2177	7.1687	.0000	1.1317	1.9896
MSMA	.5870	.0545	10.7739	.0000	.4797	.6944
TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS						
Total effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.5870	.5450	10.7339	.0000	.4797	.6944	
Direct effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.3023	.0622	4.8604	.0000	.1797	.4248	
Indirect effect of X on Y						
	Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI		
MAL	.2848	.0474	.1909	.3782		

Social media advertising positively related to Advertising literacy is supported, with results showing an interaction value of ULCI (1.8103) and LLCI (0.9747), hence, the positive values support the first hypothesis. Moreover, ($p=0.000 < 0.10$) and the coefficient value of 0.6313 signals a positive relationship between Social media advertisement and Advertising literacy i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising results in a change of advertising literacy by 0.6313.

4.7. Model 2 Summary

The value of R shows that the relation between Advertising literacy and purchase intention 67.9%. The value of R square is 46.14%, which shows that there is 46.14% variation in purchase intention due to inter linkage with advertising literacy. The value of F ($F=99.3677$) and $p=0.000$ show that the model is good suited.

4.8. Direct effect of X on Y

The results show an interaction value of ULCI (0.4248) and LLCI (0..1797), and since both values are positive, the hypothesis is supported. Furthermore, ($p=0.000 < 0.10$) and the coefficient value of 0.3023 show a positive relationship between Social media advertisement and Purchase intention i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising results in 0.3023 unit change in Purchase intention.

4.9. Indirect effect of X on Y

The values of Boot ULCI (0.3782) and Boot LLCI (0.1909) informs that the indirect influence of Social Media Advertising (X) on Purchase Intention(Y) through the mediation of Advertising Literacy is positive and significant as both values are positive. This result supports and proves the 5th hypothesis of the study.

Social media advertising – influencer review – purchase intention

4.10. Model = 4

Y = MPI

X = MSMA

M = MIR

Table 5
Sample size = 235

Outcome: Influencer review						
Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.6518	.4249	.2891	172.1258	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	Se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.0888	.2140	5.0874	.0000	.6671	1.5104
MSMA	.7027	.0536	13.1197	.0000	.5972	.8082
Outcome: Purchase Intention						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.6565	.4310	.2561	87.8838	2.0000	232.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	Se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
constant	1.1351	.2123	5.3463	.0000	.7168	1.5535
MAL	.3908	.0617	6.3384	.0000	.2693	.5123
MSMA	.3124	.0665	4.6693	.0000	.1814	.4434
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL						
Outcome: MPI						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.5766	.3325	.2991	116.0763	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	Se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5607	.2177	7.1687	.0000	1.1317	1.9896
MSMA	.5870	.0545	10.7739	.0000	.4797	.6944
TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS						
Total effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	T	p	LLCI	ULCI	
.5870	.5450	10.7339	.0000	.4797	.6944	
Direct effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	T	p	LLCI	ULCI	
.3124	.0665	4.6993	.0000	.1814	.4434	
Indirect effect of X on Y						
	Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI		
MIR	.2746	.0528	.1868	.3960		

4.11. Analysis Notes

Bootstrap confidence intervals: 1000

Level of confidence: 95.00

4.12. Interpretation: Model 1 Summary

In Model 1 summary, the value of R shows that the relation between Social media advertising and Influencer review is 65.18%. The value of R square is 42.4%, which exhibits the amount of variation in Influencer review due to Social media advertising is 42.4%. The value of $F=172.12$ and $p=0.000$, shows that the model is good suited.

The results show an interaction value of ULCI (0.8082) and LLCI (0.5972), and as both values are positive, Social media advertising is positively related to Influencer review is supported. Furthermore, the value of coefficient of 0.7027 and ($p=0.000 < 0.10$) show a positive relationship between Social media advertising and Influencer review. That is one unit alteration in Social media advertising will consequence in a change in influencer review by 0.7027 units.

4.13. Model 2 Summary

The value of R in Model 2 summary shows that relationship between Influencer review and Purchase intention is 65.6% and the value of R square is 43.1%, which demonstrates that there is 43.1% variation in Purchase Intention due to interaction with Influencer review variable of the study. The value of $F=87.8838$ and $p=0.000$, shows that the model is good suited.

4.14. Direct effect of X on Y

The results show an interactive value of ULCI (0.4434) and LLCI (0.1814), and as both values are positive, hence, it is supported (Social media advertising is positively related to purchase intention. Furthermore, the value of coefficient of 0.3124 and ($p=0.000 < 0.10$), which show a positive relationship between Social media advertising and purchase intention i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising t will cause purchase intention to change by 0.3124 units.

4.15. Indirect effect of X on Y

The values of Boot ULCI (0.3960) and Boot LLCI (0.1868) indicate that the indirect influence of Social media advertising(X) on Purchase Intention(Y) through the mediation of Influencer review is positive and significant, as both values are positive. The results support and prove the 6th hypothesis of the study.

Social media advertising – E-lifestyle – purchase intention

Model = 4

$Y = MPI$

$X = MSMA$

$M = MEL$

4.16. Analysis Notes

Bootstrap confidence intervals: 1000

Level of confidence: 95.00

4.17. Interpretation: Model 1 Summary

In Model 1 summary, the value of R shows that the relation between Social media advertising and E-lifestyle is 52.02%. The value of R square is 27.07%, which shows that the measure of variation in E-lifestyle due to Social media advertising is 27.07%. The value of $F= 86.4628$ and $p=0.000$, shows that the model is good suited.

Table 6
Sample size: 235

Outcome: E-lifestyle						
Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5202	.2707	.3622	86.4628	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	Coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	1.5834	.2396	6.6096	.0000	1.1114	2.0554
MSMA	.5575	.0600	9.2985	.0000	.4394	.6756
Outcome: Purchase Intention						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.7352	.5405	.2068	136.4319	2.0000	232.0000	.0000
Model						
	Coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.7575	.1973	3.8399	.0000	.3688	1.1462
MAL	.5072	.0495	10.2462	.0000	.4097	.6048
MSMA	.3042	.0531	5.7349	.0000	.1997	.4088
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL						
Outcome: MPI						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5766	.3325	.2991	116.0763	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	Coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5607	.2177	7.1687	.0000	1.1317	1.9896
MSMA	.5870	.0545	10.7739	.0000	.4797	.6944
TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS						
Total effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.5870	.5450	10.7339	.0000	.4797	.6944	
Direct effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.3042	.0531	5.7349	.0000	.1997	.4088	
Indirect effect of X on Y						
	Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI		
MEL	.2828	.0445	.2054	.3795		

The results show an interaction value of ULCI (0.6756) and LLCI (0.4394), and as both values are positive, Social media advertising positively related to E-lifestyle is supported. Furthermore, the value of coefficient of 0.5575 and ($p=0.000 < 0.10$) show a positive relationship between Social media advertising and E-lifestyle i.e. one unit Social media advertising will result in a change in E-lifestyle by 0.5575 units.

4.18. Model 2 Summary

The value of R in Model 2 summary shows that relationship between E-lifestyle and Purchase Intention is 57.6% and the value of R square is 33.2%, which shows that there is 33.2% alteration in Purchase Intention due to inter connection with E-lifestyle. The value of $F=116.0763$ and $p=0.000$, shows that the model is good suited.

4.19. Direct effect of X on Y

The results show an interactive value of ULCI (0.4088) and LLCI (0.1997), and as both values are positive, hence, it is supported (Social media advertising is positively related to Purchase Intention. Furthermore, the value of coefficient of 0.3042 and (p=0.000 < 0.10), which show a positive relationship between Social media advertising and purchase intention i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising will cause Purchase Intention to change by 0.3042 units.

Table 7
Sample size = 235

Outcome: Brand awareness						
Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5790	.3352	.2946	117.4953	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5907	.2160	7.3634	.0000	1.1651	2.0163
MSMA	.5861	.0541	10.8395	.0000	.4795	.6926
Outcome: Purchase Intention						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.7325	.5366	.2086	134.3002	2.0000	232.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.6744	.2018	3.3410	.0000	.2767	1.0720
MAL	.5572	.0551	10.1064	.0000	.4485	.6658
MSMA	.2605	.0558	4.6680	.0000	.1505	.3704
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL						
Outcome: MPI						
Model summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5766	.3325	.2991	116.0763	1.0000	233.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5607	.2177	7.1687	.0000	1.1317	1.9896
MSMA	.5870	.0545	10.7739	.0000	.4797	.6944
TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS						
Total effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.5870	.5450	10.7339	.0000	.4797	.6944	
Direct effect of X on Y						
Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI	
.2605	.0558	4.6680	.0000	.1505	.3704	
Indirect effect of X on Y						
	Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI		
MEL	.3265	.0478	.2420	.4366		

4.20. Indirect effect of X on Y

The values of Boot ULCI (0.3795 and Boot LLCI (0.2054) indicate that the indirect influence of Social media advertising (X) on Purchase Intention (Y) through the mediation of E-lifestyle is positive and significant, as both values are positive. The results support and prove the 7th hypothesis of the study.

Social media advertising – Brand awareness– purchase intention

Model = 4

Y = MPI

M = MBA

4.21. Analysis Notes

Bootstrap confidence intervals: 1000

Level of confidence: 95.00

4.22. Interpretation: Model 1 Summary

The value of R shows that the relation is 57.9% between Social media advertising and Brand awareness. The measurement of R square is 33.5%, which depicts the change in Brand awareness, due to Social media advertising, is 33.5%. the value F=117.4953 and p=0.000, shows that the model is good suited.

Social media advertising positively related to Brand awareness is supported, with results showing an interaction value of ULCI (0.6926) and LLCI (0.4795), hence, the positive values support the variables. Moreover, (p=0.000 < 0.10) and the coefficient value of 0.5861 indicates a positive relationship between Social media advertising and Brand awareness i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising results in a change of Brand awareness by 0.5861.

4.23. Model 2 Summary

The value of R shows that the relationship between Purchase Intention and Brand awareness is 73.2%. The value of R square is 53.6%, which demonstrates that there is 53.6% alteration in Purchase Intention due to interconnection with Brand awareness. The value of F (F=134.3002) and p=0.000 show that the model is good fitted.

4.24. Direct effect of X on Y

The results show an interaction value of ULCI (0.3704) and LLCI (0.1505), and since both values are positive, the hypothesis is supported. Furthermore, (p=0.000 < 0.10) and the coefficient value of 0.2605 show a positive relationship between Social media advertising and Purchase intention i.e. one unit change in Social media advertising results in 0.2605 unit change in Purchase Intention.

4.25. Indirect effect of X on Y

The values of Boot UCLI (0.4366) and Boot LLCI (0.2420) indicate that the indirect influence of Social media advertising (X) on Purchase Intention(Y) through the mediation of Brand awareness is positive and significant as both values are positive. This result supports and proves the 8th hypothesis of the study.

5. Discussion

In this research work, a new framework was constructed after reviewing some existing research articles. A research gap was found out after going through different studies. The foremost and first purpose of this study was to test the framework that has been projected. The evaluation of the variables of framework was the main objective. Every variable has its own reliability, and the relationships with each other are backed up by the information from the

literature section. The variables taken into consideration in this study are Social media advertising, Purchase Intention, E-lifestyle, Brand awareness, Influencer review and Advertising Literacy. In this we have one independent variable that is social media advertising and one dependent variable that is Purchase Intention. Rest variables such as Advertising Literacy, Influencer review, E-lifestyle and Brand awareness are taken as mediators. These variables were examined properly, and significant links were developed between them. Every mediator was studied with independent and dependent variable.

5.1. Conclusion

The important goal of this study was to explain the conclusive knowledge about how the social media advertising leads to purchase intention by consumers, through the mediation of advertising literacy, brand awareness, E-lifestyle, Influencer review. If consumers are getting to see social media advertisements then the brand is being successful to grab their attention. But if the mediators like influencer review step in with advertisements then consumers have a great chance to go for purchase intention. When consumers interact with a brand and is aware of that brand and its products and services then these social media advertisements and brand awareness makes him to go for purchase intention. The higher the awareness the more chances of purchase would be. If the consumers understands what is explained in social media advertisements, this advertising literacy will help brands and consumer may go for purchase intention. This current study has distinctly explained the variables and their relationship with each other. It also defines how independent variable and the mediators effect the dependent variable. The current research not only enhanced the research on these relationships, but it also widened the research by adding e-lifestyle, brand awareness, influencer review and advertising literacy, which are variables that stays under the shadow of social media advertising affecting purchase intention. Brands are focusing more on digitilization especially in the form of advertising. Brand managers are taking quick actions how to attain customer's attention by incorporating various social media activities and elements in the form of social media advertising.

5.2. Limitations

This study focus is upon social media advertising while the same study can be adopted for further research. It not be limited to any marketing or advertising method, but will be generalized. The sampling size is limited to 230 responses which can be increased to get accurate results. The sample population was limited to Pakistan only so this study can be extended in other countries as well. This research is limited to only six variables whereas it can be extended further to give us more knowledge for better results. There's a chance of people not giving honest responses as the data was collected by survey questionnaire. Other methods like observations could have been used to gather consumer responses first-handed.

5.3. Future Implications

Instead of using purposive sampling technique other methods like random sampling or convenience sampling can be used to gather various range of data data and in this way more responses can be collected as well. Since social media advertising and purchase intention are vast concepts, future researches can be more in depth and more variables can be a part of it for example viral advertisement campaign, electronic word of mouth etc. Longitudinal studies should be conducted over a longer period of time in more valuable way. The study's scope can be extended to different sectors as well.

5.4. Theoretical Implications

Firstly. The current study will assist researcher in increasing pivotal interaction and understanding of the variables. Also, this will add on to the world of knowledge already written about these variables. This research has been developed to provide and examine detailed explanations. The social media marketing theory of David Chaffey (Chaffey, 2002) was used in this crucial study to create a framework of variables. This study helped in explaining how these variables are related to one another. It demonstrated the process through which the correlation between variables happened. The current study illustrates that dependent and independent variables both supports the mediators provided by social media advertisements. A customer will not relate with brands that are entirely unrelated to them. Bonds and awareness are settled on the basis of similarity and liking. The more of awareness of the brand , the more satisfaction from the product leads to more purchases. Consumers will only refer specific brands to others if the are well aware of the brand and which are being trending.

5.5. Practical Implications

Social media advertising is a critical part for marketing strategies of businesses. As businesses are adopting more social media advertisement culture, there will be a strong need to learn its impact on target market conversion. That is turning possible customers into actual customers. Social media platforms are evolving constantly with latest features being introduced and old ones being ease off. The business needs to stay in touch with the latest techniques and to gain knowledge about target market. Social media advertisement may become more sophisticated in future due to emergence of better technology. In future, businesses can leverage this to improve social media advertisement efforts. Social media advertisements often feature public figures or celebrities. There is a great path for more research in this emerging subject. The awareness gathered will be useful for brand and marketing managers in generating new campaigns. As managers would be well aware of their consumer's liking and disliking through the success ratio of advertisements delivered. Influencer review and social media advertising can be used as a strong tool to build brand awareness. Promotions of brand and reviews can help businesses reach largest audience and may help to achieve their

vision. E-lifestyle brands should focus on content that is more liked by consumers. This includes blog posts, videos, social media updates etc. Such engaging content will build brand awareness and increase following.

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